

International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management (IJMFM)

ISSN: 2348 –3954 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 –2546 (Print)

Available online at :

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-2issue-4-may-2014>

Email us: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and subscription information:

<http://www.arseam.com/>

ORIGIN OF REALITY SHOWS AND ITS PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT ON YOUTH.

Sanjeev Sharma.

Assistant Teacher, L.S.Raheja College Commerce,
Santacruz West Mumbai, Maharashtra, India

INTRODUCTION:

Reality television is a different genre of television programme that documents natural situations and actual occurrences, and often features a new face or totally new cast. The genre often produces a emotional personal drama and conflict to a much greater extent than any non-fiction such as documentary shows. The genre has set various standard , such as reality TV confessionals used by crew and cast members to express their feelings and thoughts, which often double as the shows' is narrated . In competition-based reality shows, a very common elements such as one participant being eliminated per episode, a panel of judges, and the concept of immunity in the process of elimination.

The genre of reality shows began in western countries and European countries in the early to mid-1990s with The Real World. It then started to explode as a phenomenon in the late 1990s and early 2000s with the global success of those reality shows like Survivor and Big Brother.^[1] These shows and a many number of other shows (competition-based) became franchises in third world nation or undeveloped nation, telecasting local versions in dozens of countries in various language. Reality television as a whole has become a future of television programming. In the United States, various channels have revamp themselves to focus on reality TV, example MTV, which began in the 1980s as a sole music videos provider, and then switching to various-reality format in the early 2000s.

There are many areas around a reality television such as documentaries, television news, sports television, talk shows and traditional game shows are classified as reality television, even though they

contain all elements of reality television, such as unscripted situations and sometimes unknown participants. Other genres that predate the reality television boom have sometimes been grouped into reality TV, like hidden camera shows such as *Candid Camera* (1948), talent hunt shows such as *The Original Amateur Hour* (1948), documentaries about ordinary people such as the *Up Series* (1964), high end concept game shows such as *The Dating Game* (1965), home improvement shows such as *This Old House* (1979) and court shows featuring real-life cases such as *The People's Court* (1981).

Reality television has faced many and valid significant criticism since its rise in popularity. Much of the criticism was all centered around the use of the word "reality", and such shows' attempt to present themselves in a series of events that have occurred. Critics have argued that reality television shows do not present reality in ways both as participants being placed in different artificial situations and deceptive or even fraudulent, such as misleading editing, trained participants being coached in such a way about what to say or how to behave, storylines generated ahead of time, and scenes being staged or created for the cameras. Other criticisms of reality television shows is that it intends to humiliate and exploit participants specifically competition shows, that they make celebrities out of untalented people who is not even close to fame, and that they publicise vulgarity and materialism.

ORIGIN

TV formats portraying ordinary people in a natural and unscripted situations are very old format. Producer and host Allen Funt's *Candid Camera*, in which unsuspecting people were tested and confronted with funny, unusual situations and filmed by a hidden camera, first aired in 1948, and is often seen as a pre type of reality TV programming.^{[2][3]}

1940s–1950s

There are many incidents for television that portrayed viewers in unscripted situations began in the late 1940s. *Queen for a Day* (1945-1964) was an early example of reality-based television. The 1946 television game show *Cash and Carry* sometimes featured various contestants performing all stunts. Debuting in 1948, Allen Funt's hidden camera *Candid Camera* show earlier in 1947 radio show, *Candid Microphone* broadcast ordinary people reacting to sudden pranks.^[4] In 1948, talent search shows *Ted Mack's Original Amateur Hour* and *Arthur Godfrey's Talent Scouts* featured new and talented competitors and audience would vote for theme.

during 1950s, game shows like *Beat the Clock* and *Truth or Consequences* involved contestants in wacky and shaky competitions, stunts, plus practical jokes. 5 deleted The radio series *Nightwatch* (1951–1955) tape-recorded the daily activities of Culver City, California police officers. The series *You Asked for It* (1950–1959) incorporated audience involvement by basing episodes around requests sent in by postcard from viewers.

1960s–1970s

First broadcast in the United Kingdom in 1964, the Granada Television television documentary 'seven up' broadcast interviews with a dozen ordinary seven-year-olds from a broad cross section of society and inquired about their reactions to everyday life. Every seven years, a film documented the life of the same individuals during the intervening period, titled the *Up Series*, episodes include "7 Plus Seven", "21 Up", etc. (It is still ongoing.) The series was structured as a series of interviews with no element of script or plot, that so unique. However, it had a effect of turning ordinary people into celebrities.

The first reality show in the modern sense had been the American Broadcasting Company series "The American Sportsman", which ran from 1965 to 1986.^{[6][7]} the episode featuring one or more celebrities, and sometimes with their family members, along with a camera crew on an outdoor adventure, such as hunting, fishing, hiking, scuba diving, rock climbing, wildlife photography, horseback riding, race car driving, and the like, with most of the resulting action and dialogue being unscripted and not planned, except for the narration.

In the 1966 Direct Cinema film *Chelsea Girls*, Andy Warhol filmed various acquaintances with no direction given; the *Radio Times Guide to Film 2007* stated that the film was "to blame for reality television".^[8]

The 12-part 1973 PBS series *An American Family* showed a nuclear family (filmed in 1971) going through a divorce; it is like many other reality shows, it was like a documentary in purpose and style. In 1974 a similar counterpart program, *The Family*, was made in the UK, following the working class Wilkins family of Reading.^[9] Other front runners of modern reality television were the 1970s productions house of Chuck Barris: "The Dating Game", *The Newlywed Game*, and *The Gong Show*, all of which featured participants who were display some of their privacy and dignity in a televised or game competition.^[10] In 1978, "Living in the Past" made the contestants feel the life in an Iron Age English village.

1980s-1990s

Producer George Schlatter capitalized on the advent of videotape to create *Real People*, a surprise hit for NBC which ran from 1979 to 1984. The success of *Real People* was quickly copied by production house ABC with "That's Incredible", based on stunts done by contestants co-hosted by Fran Tarkenton.

Canadian TV ran a show "Thrill of a Lifetime", a fantasies-fulfilled reality show from 1982 to 1988 .

In 1985, underwater cinematographer Al Giddings tying with former Miss America Shawn Weatherly on the NBC series "Oceanquest". Which featured miss shawn Weatherly's in an adventurous reality show showing her doing scuba diving in various exotic locations. And Weatherly was nominated for an "Emmy Award" for Outstanding Achievement in informational programming.^[11]

COPS, which first aired in the spring of 1989 and,^[12] showed police officers on duty apprehending criminals; with the camcorder look and cinema feel of much for reality television.

The series Nummer 28, which first aired on netherland the year television in 1991, originated a new concept of putting strangers in the same environment for an extended period of time and recording those drama and emotions that ensued. . One year later, the same concept was used by MTV in their new and inspired series from nummer 28, "The Real World" .^[13]

According to television commentator Charlie Brooker, this type of reality television had been possible only by the advent of computer based non-linear editing systems for video produced. These systems made quickly edits and hours of video footage into a usable forms, something which was very difficult to do before..^[15]

The TV show *Expedition Robinson*, produce by tv producer Charlie Parsons, which first aired in 1997 in Sweden and was later produced in various other countries titled "Survivor", with the same idea of reality shows like *Number 28/Real World* of competition and elimination, in which cast members/contestants battled against each other and were removed from the show until only one winner remained.

2000s

Reality television saw a bombardment or explosions of global popularity in the late 1990s and early 2000s, with the successes of reality shows like the *Big Brother* and *Survivor/Expedition Robinson* format of franchises.

However, this proved to be the case that shows like *Survivor* and *American Idol* both topped the US season-average television ratings in the 2000s.

Internationally, a number of shows created in the late 1990s and 2000s have had tasted global success. At least nine reality-television franchises have had over 30 international adaptations each whether it was the singing competition franchises Idols, Star Academy or The X Factor, and other competition franchises like Survivor/Expedition Robinson, Big brother, Got Talent, Top Model, Master Chef and Dancing with the Stars etc. Several reality game shows from the same period found greater success, including shows like Deal or No Deal, Who Wants to Be a Millionaire and Weakest Link, with over 50 international adaptations each

In India too, the show Indian Idol was the most popular television program for its first six seasons.^[17]

During the early part of the 2000s, network executives expressed concern that reality-television programming was limited in its appeal and therefore DVD reissue should be done. DVDs for reality shows in fact sold briskly; Laguna Beach: The Real Orange County, The Amazing Race, Project Runway, and America's Next Top Model all ranked in the top DVDs sold on social networking sites like Amazon.com, shows such as Fear Factor, cops and Wife Swap in which each episode is self-contained was rerun and fairly and easily gain popularity, but usually only on cable television and/or during the daytime (COPS and America's Funniest Home Videos being exceptions). Season-long competitions such as The Amazing Race, Survivor, and America's Next Top Model generally perform more poorly and usually must be rerun in marathons to draw the necessary viewers to make it worthwhile. Even in these cases, it is not always successful: Dancing with the Stars was picked up for a ten-season run on game show network in 2012 and was run in marathon format, but experienced and performed with very poor ratings. Another option is to create documentaries around series including extended interviews with the participants and outtakes not seen in the original airings; the syndicated series American Idol Rewind is an example of innovative and creative strategy.

COPS has had or made huge success through direct response sales and DVD. A fox staple since 1989, COPS has, as of 2013, outlasted all competing scripted police shows. Another series that has seen wide success is called "Cheaters", which has been running since 2000 in the US and is franchised in over 100 countries worldwide.

In 2001, the Academy of Television Arts and Sciences added a new category the reality show genre to the Emmy Awards with the category of Outstanding Reality Program. In 2003, to better differentiate between competition and informational reality programs, a second category, Outstanding Reality-Competition Program, was added. In 2008, a third category, Outstanding Host for a Reality or Reality-Competition Program, was also added.

2010s

In 2010, "The Tester" was the show which became the first reality television show based on a video game console.^[19]

By 2012, many of the long-running reality television show franchises in the United States, such as American Idol, Dancing with the Stars and The Bachelor, had begun to see declining ratings.^[20] However, reality television as a whole remained highly durable in the U.S., with hundreds of shows across many channels. In 2012 New York Magazine's Vulture blog published a humorous Venn diagram showing popular themes across American reality shows then running, including shows set in the U.S. states of Alaska, Louisiana and Texas, shows about cakes, weddings and pawnbrokers, and shows, usually competition-based, whose title includes the word "Wars".^[21]

The Voice, a singing competition franchise created by John de Mol that was started in 2010 and was the newest highly successful reality television franchise, with almost 50 international adaptations.

Duck Dynasty, a reality series featuring the Robertson and his family that founded Duck Commander in 2013 and became the most popular reality series in U.S. cable television history. Its fourth season premiere was almost viewed by nearly 12 million viewers in the United States, most of which were in

rural markets; its rural audience share has ranked in the 30s, an extremely high number for any series, broadcast or cable.^[22]

In india

The trend of reality television had already started and caught attention in India in the 1990's with music and dance based talent shows such as Meri Awaaz Suno on Doordarshan (government owned public broadcaster), and Sa Re Ga Ma on Zee TV (India's first privately owned channel network) and others. It was from these shows that the talent of the then very young Sunidhi Chauhan and Shreya Ghoshal, the two most sought-after female and popular voices today in the Mumbai film industry, were spotted. Boogie Woogie, a dance reality show on Sony hosted by Javed Jafri the first dance based reality show nurtured many a talent like the Prince Dance Group from the backwaters of Orissa. Since India has had a rich tradition of music and dance, these reality shows provided golden opportunities and another platform for showcasing the vast reserves of untapped talent across the country without any discrimination on the basis of gender or class. A career in the film industry was the greatest prize of them all. Many more success stories were to follow and reality television became the rage in small town India. Ambitious parents were seen pushing their children, both girls and boys to become stars on the small screen. The reality shows showing talents had the capability to turn a simple and ordinary man a celebrity and his career to start off.

It was welcome after studying the international television scenario, Indian industry too catches the latest trends, after the audiences were fed up and tired of watching saas bahu sagas that are still not lose hold among viewers.

The talent show itself became an indicator of the new India which was aspirational. It was realized that television could also be something more than entertainment and it was changing the culture as the new generation of women were ready to get exploit it in equal measure as men. Conservative middle class parental attitudes towards girls also seemed to have undergone tremendous change as parents were seen supporting their daughters in every possible way to help them appear on television. While the participants of these shows were mostly youngsters with many dreams and possibilities of a career ahead of them, shows such as Mother's Series on Boogie Woogie took the show to other level and gave an opportunity to women whose talent had taken a back-seat once they had become housewives and mothers. Many of the women participants had left homes and families behind in the care of their husbands, mothers or even their mothers in law to get their share of limelight. It has also been interesting to observe certain shifts in the attitude of the joint family structure which has begun to take pride in the accomplishments of its women and their children and allows them to step out so long as they return to resume their roles within the family.

Adapting and getting inspired from international shows started right in the 1990s. In 1992, Roshan Abbas hosted the programme Wheel of Fortune, modelled on an eponymous American game show. However, the trend of adopting global formats intensified after the success of Kaun Banega Crorepati (KBC). The 2000 show, which was hosted by Bollywood megastar Amitabh Bachchan and was based on American show "who wants to be a millionaire"

Though India too produces some original and audience favourites reality shows like Saanp Seedi, Sa Re Ga Ma Pa, Antakshri, Tol Mol Ke Bol, and Boogie Woogie before the advent of 20th century but Kaun Banega Crorepati was a milestone and then Indian broadcasters never looked back and made the desi version of those reality shows cult which were a huge success in western countries. Some of the shows adopted formats post KBC are Indian Idol from (Pop Idol), Jhalak Dikhhla Jaa (Dancing with Stars), Bigg Boss (Big Brother).

I am very much fond of watching television and follower of new show or the traditional one, right from my school days. But now i am working couldn't spent time on watching shows for more than two to three hours, I have become choosy, in last 10 years reality shows in india have shown promises among Indian audiences including myself. I am such a viewer who is excited to anticipate the next episode outcome, but I am very curious whether like me other youngster too is psychologically attracted towards reality shows as these reality shows have different reasons and genre and there it lies the under lying motive to make viewers watch such shows. First of all a reality show when it was started in india around in the year 2000, it was all about a non celebrity or a volunteer who would participate in such shows and reality shows cameras would catch their reactions in a face to face situations, this part somewhere psychologically connected the show with the audience mind and mentally they felt that its just not a common man participating a reality show but they are real and normal who are representing the viewers. This is why shows like k.b.c, saaregamapa , india's got talent etc, are biggest hit on t.v because the viewers somewhere in deep of their hearts sympathises and empathizes with the show's contestants. But whether they are psychologically affected in a good way or the bad way, we cant say that but yes we can make out by analysing the effects on society. And this analysis are dependent upon viewer's desires and motives as the viewers see themselves in these realty shows contestants and through them these stars are earning their bread and butter, if you see any reality show, each one of them portrays certain desires like power, influence, travel, living, exit, survival, honour, revenge etc the biggest effect socially and psychologically that a viewer or audience will never make out that how people compromise with different situations to survive their well being and self worthiness, it has definitely affected our real thinking .

We can definitely see its effect psychologically when people interact differently with others, not been able to handle or deal with various situations, and challenges with that brave heart, its because they feel the sense of pleasure and satisfaction when they watch these reality shows and remove their frustration being reel part rather than in solving the reality or individual handling scenarios, problems, dilemmas, sadness, depression, frustration, emptiness etc on their own. This part will study the psychological aspect of reality shows on youth.

According to researcher(gardyn, 2001), main streaming television programming has been dominated by reality shows being a source of not so costly entertainment for viewers.

The statement was said 13 years back, but nobody knew that it will fit in Indian context as Indian television and broad casting industry has seen number of reality shows flooded on Indian satellite television airspace, shows ranging from talent hunt, make over, emotional drama, vengeance, voyeurism, celebrity etc so you can see how reality show provide all facets of emotional content in one show therefore a viewer feels that why to switch to melodrama shows based on mother in law and daughter in law, rather the touth viewers of today get everything in one reality show based on friend ship, love, ego, hatred, competition etc. Thus reality shows are dominating and upcoming force in next 5 years from now.

The under lying concept of any reality shows is that individual or viewer should feel identical with the characters on reality shows with them selves in real life and forget their personal life problem and give their 100 % whether it is about their participation, for fame, for monetary benefits or help to win their favourite characters or contestants in reality show.

According to a published journal doing research on sexuality and social policy indicated that those adolescent kids more exposed to television resulted in less body satisfaction considering their self esteem and body image, more sexual urge and requires parental guidance while watching television.(Donnerstein, E., Slaby, R., & Eron, L. (1992). Television and film violence. In American Psychological Association, Draft report of the Commission on Violence and Youth. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association)

In a recent study by Norma pecora, John P. Murray, Ellen A. Wartella, (2006) the research team showed that kids watching violence had an increased heart rate also demonstrated fear, and not only that they also stored the observed violence in an area of the brain proving to be a traumatic event in long run.

A study in New Zealand involving 1000 people from childhood to 26 years of age proved that those kids involving children and adolescence who watched maximum television had poor educational achievement when they turn 12 or not been able to reach school or university.

According to researcher, shows like world wrestling entertainment over the past years had a strong impact on society youth as they are exposed to violence, sex and vulgarity and approximate they can spend six hours to watch them. (Grimes, William, G, 2012)

It is clear from above researchers that children right from the age 5 to 25 are exposed to violence, sexual content, vulgarity, etc at a very tender age where they don't find parents to discuss these sensitive issues specially Indian parents who hesitate to talk to their kids on topics like sexual organs, abusive language etc. Exposure of kids towards fighting reality shows like world wrestling entertainment which are telecasted on channels like star sports and ten sport are major attraction among youth, its not only television viewing but they are even exposed to fighting games at a very raw age.

Recent research shows sign of extreme violence involving teens and associated links to violent video games have led to an increased interest in video game violence. Research suggests that violent video games influence aggressive behavior, aggressive affect, aggressive cognition, and physiological arousal, (Steven J. Kirsh (2003))

And by advent of reality show the youth started getting the dose of vulgarity, abusive language, voyeurism etc in tandem, almost on every channel and few reality show that they were exposed to,

While researchers like (Dauncey, 1996), (Kaminer, 2000), (Reiss and Wiltz, 2004) too also believed and presented their argument against reality show as their contents are too low in quality, their characters are questioned on social validity, and portrays extreme exhibition of culture and voyeurism.

While there are also researchers who talk in favour of reality show and that too in favour of reality TV producers who will definitely go for low cost budget rather than high cost fiction show. (Gardyn 2001, Kilborn 1994).

But in India, reality shows production cost too much because it reproduces foreign reality show format and thus pays huge amount on technology transfer know how, expertise and royalty payment but are happy already stamp of popularity achieved in foreign countries, so to get back their returns that they invested in making a reality show, they resort to all tactics that can get attention of viewers especially youth and top of the show thus to attract sponsors and advertisers respectively. (Lauhana Ganguly, 2012).

Today's viewers not only watch reality show, but also has become a part of those reality shows, i.e. participate in those shows. (Andrejevic, 2002, Wong, 2001, Kilborn, 1994).

The producer of the reality shows use all tantra and mantra to get or reach maximum people i.e. talented contestants, beautiful and handsome contestants, region wise and linguistic wise selected contestants, contestants who are back biters, abuser, popular etc have been able to draw attention of viewers who would vote for their favourite contestants.

Even researchers like (Fetviet 1999, Mendelson and Papacharissi, 2005) debate fiction and non fiction shows and how viewers grasp reality shows and fictional shows.

What sets apart reality show and non reality show is that reality show provides an element of surprise, their characters can be a common man whose life is somehow identifiable with the viewers life. The viewers believe that reality shows are all in all entertainment potential and are placed exactly the non reality shows.

This section will discuss the growing popularity of this creative and innovative genre and its consequences on audience or viewers mind, it will also discuss different psychological theories on attitude, behaviour and attention of viewers of reality shows.

(A. Rubin,1994, p.420) in his contemporary uses and gratification theory places five assumptions:

1. Communication and media selection is all behaviour oriented influenced by goal direction, purposive and motivation.
2. Selection of communication vehicles by viewers is only to satisfy their feeling of needs and desires
3. There are many host of socio- psychological factors that are imitated by people while they communicate.
4. Media wit fully uses other forms of communication to compete to get attention and describe our gratification of our needs and behaviour.
5. People prove to be more influential than media in communication behaviour.

In other words audience involvement and their understanding after gaining television experience have fulfilled their motives of psychological and social factor which influence their behaviour either at home or at school or at office, this behaviour is somewhere created by media who compete with other forms of communication to grab the attention of viewers and viewers themselves proves influential in transferring message to people who may be their friends, relatives or special group of friends, they only transfer when their own needs and desires gets fulfilled, otherwise they create a negative image of the same media. the underlying motives is the audience is left with less or no choice available as the channels are flooded with one or more reality every month, every year and the viewer have no experience of media content or what they are watching, they believe on popularity, availability, entertainment value.

The researcher also provides two methods 1. Instrumental 2. Ritualized method.

Instrumental method proves that viewers view reality shows are medium of getting information from it and believes the content to be realistic while ritual methods proves that viewers only view any reality shows this is their habit to consume time and some where he or she is vulnerable to more connectivity and exposure towards the medium of this genre of entertainment.

The researcher also threw light that viewers are having limited or no variations in fiction shows and they are left with few choices in them on the other way they find variations in reality shows and their content very realistic, day to day use, common man issue and problems etc also some where the circle in which viewers live like relatives, friends in bus, train, sports or social networking sites do influence a viewer's perception in grasping and understanding of reality shows as a social need every person is society oriented and needs to discuss or share happiness or sadness whether its related to their life or contents of reality shows.

(griffen- foley,2004) talks about the possible motive and traits that appeal the selection and involvement under the influence of reality show genre. His research also talked about how mass marketing strategies were adopted to promote women's magazine in war years where communication technologies were least but whatever resources had, made full utilize of it, eventually it gave birth to leading to talk shows, game shows and other reality shows.

Today, its not a war era but technically speaking, our communication medium has increased four times than the world war 2 but what we experience in 21 century is that we are surround by materialism, as it is a result of industrialization and modernization that demands employee to work for more than 12 hours to meet the expectations of the market, also leading to expansion of more urban area and migration to these areas from town and village, what has given rise is more inflation and resulting in both parents

working for survival of needs of both themselves and kids, another impact of industrialization and modernization is that it resulted in youth getting proper and market requirement degree thus leaving them spend almost 20 years to get education, so if this is the situation then from entertainment point of view, I don't think they are going to compromise and will reject such shows which doesn't fall on their expectation level i.e. they will divert attention and focus to such shows which involves them too in the entertainment where their talent like singing, dancing, eating etc get more attention, shows which talk about their problem or nation's problem, etc gave birth to shows like emotional attyachhar, Indian idol, halla bol, satyamev jayate etc.

While researchers like (jagodozinki, 2003), commenting on videos taken by viewers that were a thorough hit in 1940's on American channels, he briefs that the audience itself became the content producer and they unexpectedly or unknowingly brought their behavior to reality through the discoveries of camera and new technologies..

In 21's century too, videos taken on camera or by camera is a great hit among viewers therefore shows like mtv bakra, mtv webbed, axe your ex etc are popular among viewers and that too among youth, who want to remember every aspect of adult hood whether spending quality time with friends in college, coaching, trip or time spent with family and relatives, they want their experience to be captured and preserved for longer period of time and this could happen now with digital camera's and that too on their mobile itself, this aspect of togetherness of youth are replicated through reality shows like roadies, splitzvilla etc. plus attraction of getting on camera and its attention has expose them to be directly involved in the form of audience to be part of game shows and talent shows and even in talk shows in the form of interactive audience.

Another researcher (Thompson,2001) mentions that reality content can only be a hit when there is improvisation and contrary to viewers perception and imaginations, i.e. unpredictability.

Reality television main mantra can be fitted into four features

1. Camera surveillance in a passive position
2. illusion of reality,
3. Focus on ordinary people
4. Certain extent of voyeurism.

Many of the reality show are based on these traits, it is difficult to predict a reality show as it is combination of many genres of reality show, as it is growing and changing too like many programs on television has made this genre versatile because of its ability to adopt and surprise.(Penzhorn, Heidi, and Magriet Pitout (2007)

Several researchers also assessed the impact of reality show to the culture after viewing them, specially, jone (2003) conducted interview for big brother's fan only to find the perception that a audience really identify realness of reality shows, surprise the researcher found that the viewers are not only fond of the show but it also knew it was all artificial, created a reality show look, but what she concluded is a need to study from psychological point of the viewers that they experience sexuality, nudity and voyeurism etc from the show.

Big boss , the Indian reality show based on the same format of big brother and same technological know how and expertise is also famous among Indian youth, the reason behind is

1. It is hosted by a celebrity and bollywood actor salman khan, who has a huge fan following majorly youth.

2. The concept is unique that attract the youth, its set of people living in a house that remain isolated from rest of the world with out any contact with their family, friends or relative.
3. The contestants are not selected at random, there are celebrities who are politically acclaimed, pageant winners, item girls, international stars, criminally involved people, aspiring models, soap actors, singers, film stars, people supporting lesbian, gay, transgender community, sports person and comedian, all flavour in one show, for all strata of people.
4. Also there is a representative from common man and is selected through contest and auditions.
5. The promotional activities are done on large scale by salmaan khan and his team itself.
6. Rumours are spread well in advance about the contestants in local news paper in all languages, t.v channels, hoardings, social networking sites etc.

According to (mcCraken, 1989) concluded in his study that audience is the follower of celebrity such as actors, models, athlete, and followed their direction as they consider them their role model and aspire to become like them, now the word celebrity and reality show are two sides of the same coin.

Earlier it was difficult to hear, meet, handshake your favourite celebrity, one could hear their story through or via friend circle, relatives etc but through reality shows like big boss, dus ka dum, jhalak, comedy nights with kapil, etc as an audience we have not only been able to witness our favourite celebrity but also call them live during the show, chat and ask question face to face from your celebrity and can even share photos, videos on social networking sites with their friends and relatives.

Another researcher (nabi, biely,morgan,stitt, 2003) conducted studies focussing on viewing reasons like attitude and behaviour.

While reiss and wiltz (2004), took a different approach to measure the motive (16 motive) that appeal the viewer towards reality tv shows.

And A. Rubin (1983), way before reiss and wiltz gave nine motives to watch television and these motives are

1. Relaxation
2. Companionship,
3. Entertainment
4. Social interaction
5. Information
6. Habit
7. Pass time
8. Arousal
9. Escape

While reiss and wiltz (2004) included voyeurism as an added feature in one of the motive.

In a study made by (Michael.a. stefanne, Derek lackaff and deven rosen, 2010) identify through social cognitive theory a relation between behaviour model of reality show and viewer's behaviour on social networking sites.

Even a common man would become a celebrity and gain instant success through reality show. (reiss and wiltz, 2004) in their research witnessed reality tv as one of the dominating force that had non scribbled interaction of non celebrity actors termed as ordinary people.

This was a miracle step in television industry which provided even a simple man like you , me or sushil kumar, a computer operator from a small village in buhar, who won 5 crore rupees on kaun banega crorepati 2012,who was transformed into a celebrity. And in the era of 21st century the message of success is easily spread through newspaper, magazines, news channel, social networking sites etc .

Researchers like (Dominick,84,mcghee and frueh,80,, shanahan, scheufele,yang, and hizi,2004) also made us aware the other side of the media that is impact of media towards different attitudes like violence,sex and smoking.

In this reference (bente and feist,2000) referred reality tv as “ affect t.v” as it not only made it possible the private stories of important and less important people to mass audience but also somewhere connected with their feelings and emotions.

A survey conducted by (ferris smith, Greenberg,and smith,2007) observed that when a viewer is watching a dating reality show made a perception towards dating relationships.

(calvert 2000) supported the above perception and also feared that voyeurism form of reality tv may not be fulfilling the standard of the society and its culture and who is at the receiving end , none other than who are involved in it either physically or mentally.

Shows like emotional attyachar, roadies, splitzvilla etc does nt solve social issues like dowry, female foeticide etc but it only provide a source of entertainment and negative traits in the youth mind

Negative traits like

Personality disorder

- a. Selfish personality disorder
- b. Negative personality disorder(nihilistic personality disorder)
- c. Jealous and suspicious personality disorder

Not only this male youth develops flirtious behaviour, obscenity and attitude of lust.

Today's youth have forgotten a beauty of heart, state of lovable mental beauty and have forgotten creativity and emotional maturity.(Millon,Theodore,2004).

To better understand the viewers psychology that is turning them to reality shows or television or media, we better under stand psychological theories on motives, attitude, social psychological theory.

Motivational theories:

1. **Rational motivation:** this motivation theory talks about how human behaviour changes either for good or bad only for a reason or a explanation is needed for the change.

In a reality show too if a content is not up to the mark or fulfil the standard criteria of the society, the viewers complain to the broadcasting authority.(Ryan,Richard Edward.l.deci (2000)

2. **Intrinsic motivation:** these motivation comes from within and is driven by an interest or enjoyment in doing the task.

These type of motivation we see a lot in reality shows like roadies where people compete to do the task willingly and outperform others. shows like halla bol where a girl or women gets offended by the acts of superiors, neighbour, or friend etc their inner motivation helps them to fight back and return the feelings or sentiments they go through.(Ryan,Richard Edward.l.deci (2000)

Prof. Steven reiss mentioned 16 basic desires of intrinsic motivation that are base of all human behaviour whether earning is concerned or watching a reality show.

- a. Acceptance—means the need for approval
- b. Curiosity--- the need to learn
- c. Eating--- the need for food
- d. Family---the need to raise kids or spend some quality time with members
- e. Honour--- respect for self or for values or ethnic group.
- f. Idealism---- the need for social justice
- g. Independence---- the need for individuality or freedom
- h. Order--- disciplined and lawful environment
- i. Physical activity--- do task to survive the game
- j. Power---will power
- k. Romance----sex, beauty and voyeurism
- l. Savings----doing task and increase money
- m. Social contacts--- friends and peer relationship.
- n. Social status--- raise the standard of living
- o. Tranquillity---immunity or to be safe
- p. Vengeance----wild card entry, strike back, or compete furiously. .(reiss, steven (2002)

3. **Extrinsic motivation:** it is also called external motivation or a motivation which is desired for an outcome either responsive by an announcement of reward or declaration of punishment.(Ryan,Richard Edward.l.deci (2000)

4. **Operant conditionings:** b.f. skinner described such learning arising out of rewards and punishment and such behaviour can be observed or seen.

e.g shows contestants showing decency, abusive words, anger, etc can be observed or learnt.

5. **push and pull motivation:** this type of motivation discusses with the context of tourism attraction, need for relaxation or escapism, landscape, cultural image or climatic destinations. E.g. normally all people cannot travel therefore tourism aspect is shown on few reality shows like highway on the plate, man v/s wild, roadies and splitzvilla etc. (mannel, R.c Isho-aholas (1987)

6. content theories of motivation: a. Content theory of human motivation that too Abraham maslow's hierarchy of needs,

This hierarchy includes 1. Physiology (hunger, thirst, sleep,etc)

2. safety/ security/ shelter/ health

3. belongingness/ love/friendship.

4. self esteem/recognition/achievement.

5. self actualisation.

All these Maslow theory are applied to reality shows contestants who come from poor family or background, they have hunger to achieve fame, win lots of money to provide security to family and most important instant success throughout the country and have place in million of hearts .shows like x factors, Indian idol, dance India dance, India's got talent, guineas books of world record: ab India todega, entertainment ke liye kuchh bhi karega,sare ga ma pa etc. (. A. Maslow. (1954)

b. Alderfer's erg content theory of motivation: alderfer's just expanding maslow's theory to 1. Existence 2. Relatedness 3. Growth (Alderfer c.p (1972)

7. **Self determination theory:** this theory tests the individual behaviour in the form of self motivation, self determination, achieving self competence, relatedness and autonomy. (R.w. white (1963)

8. **Achievement theory of motivation:** this theory give relevance to adaptive motivational pattern like working hard, willingness to pick task and contributing success to efforts of team and encouraging team spirits, it believes in dominance, tolerance for risk, fear of failure etc (Atkinson, john, joelo raynor (1978)

9. **Attribution theory:** this theory believes in why any individual behaves in certain way in certain conditions i.e. causes of the event and accordingly people's behaviour. (Kassin, saul (2007)

10. **Approach and avoidance motivation:** approach motivation is something expecting positive result while avoidance motivation is something avoiding things expecting negative feelings. (Schacter, Daniel (2011)

11. **Unconscious motivation:** some motivation which are hidden and unknown. (J.a Ouellette (1998)

Socio psychological theories:

1. Intrapersonal phenomenon:

Attitude: Social psychologists have studied how attitude is formed, the base structure of various attitudes, attitudinal change, the different function of attitudes, and how various relationship exist between attitudes and behaviour. Because people are influenced by the situation like approval or disapproval, favourability or unfavourability, or likes and dislikes. Attitudes are also involved in several other areas of the discipline, such as, interpersonal attraction, conformity, social perception, and prejudice.(Kassin, Saul; Fein, Steven; Markus, Hazel Rose (2008).

Persuasion: Persuasion is an influence method of tempting people towards the adoption of an good or bad attitude, certain idea, or behavior by rational by emotive means. How persuasion is done

The Communicator, who has a good credibility, excellent expertise, and can be trusted, and he or she is attractive.

The Message, includes message consisting of reason, emotion (such as fear), one or more arguments, and many types of informational content.

The Audiences, who are from various of demographics, having many personality traits, and and too many preferences.

The medium through which they reach audience includes, radio, television, the internet, or face-to-face interactions.

Social cognition: Social cognition is a growing area of social psychology that deals with studies of how people think or perceive about others, and think about them, and recall information about others. (Aronson, Elliot; Wilson, Timothy D; Akert, Robin M (2010).

Self concept: Self-concept is a term referring to concept of confidence that people have or believe about themselves. (Markus, Hazel (1977).

Interpersonal phenomenon of social behaviour:

Social influence: the term social influence can be talked in three main reference 1. Conformity: is a behaviour of how people act or think like other members in a group. 2. Compliance: is a change in behaviour only on a request or suggestion from certain group of people. 3. obedience: is result in behaviour who follows the order and command from another person. (Cialdini, R.B (2000).

Group dynamics: A group can be defined as two or more individuals that are connected to each another emotionally or by social relationships. Groups normally interact, influence each other, and share a similar goal or common identity. (Forsyth, D.R (2006).

Case study:

how satyamev jayate: a reality show created psychological impact on viewers

Satyamev Jayate : is an Indian television talk show that was telecasted on various channels of star network along with doordarshan's dd national and the very first season of the show was premiered on 6 May 2012 successfully marked the television debut of Aamir Khan, a popular Bollywood actor and filmmaker.^[2] The second season of the show aired from 2 March 2014.^[3]

The show highlighted some evil and sensitive social issues still prevalent in India such as, child sexual abuse, dowry, honor killings, insensitivity towards the physically disabled, medical malpractice domestic violence, female foeticides overuse of pesticides leading to pesticide poisoning, alcoholism, untouchability, plight of senior citizens and water crisis. While Hindi is the language of the show, but it was also dubbed in other Indian languages like, Malayalam, Bengali, Tamil and Telugu, Marathi and subtitled in English.

Satyamev Jayate received an outstanding extra ordinary positive response and good feedback from both the as public well as the critics. The show was grasped and widely appreciated by several film and television personalities, politicians and social activists for well researched, properly edited format, out of the way presentation and strong content.

The concept of the show neither what was it related to was never revealed in the Indian media, but official song was released on several news channel, radio, and even promotional campaign was done by

aamir khan personally and a hype was created before the show officially went on air on 6 May 2012.^[2] There were also no get-togethers, parties or press conferences organized to discuss the content, leading up to the premiere of the show.^[4] However, but speculation started by various sources and reported the show to be based on "the common man" rather than being fictional.^[5] Also, the way it was based on a specific content, it was given a image of a talk show discussing social issues like child labour, health problems and other issues affecting the country.^[6] aamir Khan, who is well known not discussing his movies said that he wont talk about the show and its format and he expected from every one to see directly on t.v^[7] and also commented on the theme of the show that the show is all about connecting with common man of india and its people^[8] He also added that this show will understand the problem and suggest measures for the problem as he himself is not a big catalyst to bring change but he will definitely hear and understand, even hold their hand and hug them.^[7] the teaser of the show was released on youtube on 2nd April 2012 and promotional songs were released in 300 theatres all across india and mobile apps launched on ios and android software and ad campaign taglines " public bhethegi" " dil se dekho" "sab ka apna show" " entertainment ka matlab"

Khan was adamant about naming the show 'Satyameva Jayate' as he felt it completely gelled with the theme and psychologically it attracts a Indian mind and which indicated that the show is of, for and belongs to people of India The shooting of the show took place in several states of India and Khan travelled extensively over several weeks to various places in Rajasthan, Kashmir, Kerala, Delhi, Punjab, and in the North-East.^[7] The studio portions of the show were shot in Vrundavan Studio^[10] and Yash Raj Studios in Mumbai.^[11] However, Khan later learnt the fact that the title 'Satyameva Jayate' belonged to the country and cannot be registered for the copyrights as it cannot be exploited on a creative level for promotional activities. The team however went ahead and borrowed the title.^[12]

Special screening in villages.

Star Plus organised a special screening of the first episode of the show in some villages in Gujarat, Maharashtra and Uttar Pradesh where the villagers do not have access to television. The initiative was said to have been taken to ensure Satyamev Jayate reaches all over the country as it caters to the issues of the common people of the country. The program was screened on 6 May 2012, during the same time it was aired across the country, on community TV sets in villages like Bhingara and Kahupatta in Maharashtra, Chepa in Gujarat, Jhunkar in Madhya Pradesh, Tikeri, Lalpur, Sarauta, Khannapurwa and Maniram in Uttar Pradesh. Most of these villages are reported to have a population of less than 5,000.^[29] Gayatri Yadav from STAR India stated that, "This is an important and relevant show for all of India and Star India is going all out to make sure that this show reaches out to all Indians even in places with limited or no TV connectivity." Based on the response to its first episode, the screening of subsequent episodes in a similar manner is being considered by STAR.^[30]

Critical response

The show opened to highly positive reviews. Several media organizations praised Aamir Khan for his effort and described the show as a movement. In her review, Ritu Singh of IBN Live stated, "Aamir Khan deserves applause for bringing up such a sensitive issue and presenting it in a hard hitting way. The amount of research Aamir and his team has put into the show was clearly visible with the facts and figures presented. Every aspect of the issue was covered with great diligence." She concluded it by saying, "'Satyamev Jayate' is not just a show; it's a movement to change people's mindset."^[41] Parmita Uniyal from Hindustan Times praised the content and format of the show and said, "Aamir Khan have to step in to do what journalists are supposed to do – make a difference. The show is a classic example of that."^[42] Gayatri Sankar from Zee News described the show as an "eye opener" and commented that, "Satyamev Jayate will make you unlearn all the wrong you have learnt and discover that compassionate human your soul wishes to be. The show grips you and leaves you dumfounded! You will be left asking for more and would wish the show never ends."^[43] Trade analyst and film critic Komal Nahta commended that, "I cried while watching the show. I think people will watch it as it has touched an emotional chord."^[44] Neeraj Roy, managing director and chief executive of Hungama Digital Media Entertainment, also praised the

show by commending "Brilliant effort. Well done Aamir Khan and Satyamev Jayate. We can make a difference."^[45] Sukanya Verma from Rediff.com expressed concerns regarding the show saying, "This is a grand initiative and a sound format into which a lot has been invested -- monetarily as well as in terms of research. Deriding this show simply because it is hosted by a Bollywood actor who is also a marketing whiz, questions our credibility, not his."^[46]

Some reviewers also criticized the show on various grounds. A review from Outlook India noted that, "[...] the show might well heighten awareness, enable the efforts of those doing real work at the ground level, and get the issue out of the denial closet, [...] But it is a little unrealistic to expect a film star and a TV show to change the world."^[47] Subhash Jha from The Times of India commented on the show, "...though brave and thought provoking, was disappointing in its lack of genuine connectivity between the host and the victims of social atrocity. At the moment Satyamev Jayate looks like a product of elitist conscientiousness."^[48] Sheela Bhatt, from Rediff.com, commented that the format of Satyamev Jayate has to be more profound, and the big problem of the show is that it is on predictable lines. She went on to conclude by requesting Khan to bring in some raw energy in the show.^[49]

Viewers' Response.

The show also received positive feedback from various fields right from eminent personalities and all stratas such as social activists, media houses, film and television personalities. Political party shiv shena founder Balasaheb Thackeray, praised the show and Amir Khan for bringing out social issues in front of public.^[23] Prominent social activist and retired IPS officer Kiran Bedi described the show and said that the show is creative, evidence based, very emotional connecting and truly inspiring. ^[50] while commenting that, it is an expression of the inner power of media and its inherent potential of society in resolving its own problems."^[44] Noted film actress Shabana Azmi too appreciated the show for its research and emotional touch and content and referred Amir Khan's show as a revolutionary. Thoroughly researched covers all aspects touches emotional chord n forces us to reexamine ourselves.^[50] While film producer Ekta Kapoor proclaimed and went one step ahead mentioned the show as the best show of the decade, film directors Madhur Bhandarkar and Farhan Akhtar also praised the show commenting that the show brought the expected and desired change and that too on to the small screen^[51] Other high personalities who lauded the show were Salman Khan,^[52] Preity Zinta, Dia Mirza, Boman Irani, Neha Dhupia, Mandira Bedi, Kabir Bedi, Mini Mathur, Kabir Khan, Maria Goretti, Vishal Dadlani, Ken Ghosh, Harsha Bhogle & Pritish Nandy.^{[50][53][54][55]}

Apart from the critics, film, social and political personalities, the show was well received by the television viewers many describing it as very gutsy, hard-hitting and sensible program that strikes an emotional chord with all sets of audiences."^[56] As per Indiantelevision.com, the show garnered an overall rating of 4.27 television ratings (TVR) (including terrestrial of DD) across the 6 metropolitan cities: Delhi, Mumbai, Kolkata, Chennai, Bangalore and Hyderabad, upon its premiere telecast on 6 May 2012.^[57] According to the Television Audience Measurement (TAM), the show reached out to 8.96 million people in the age group of 4+. One hundred thousand people tried calling in from across the country to speak to Khan during the show out of which 10 or 11 people could eventually get through.^[58]

On its premiere day, several topics related to the show were seen trending on the social networking sites like twitter,facebook occupying the top five trends on these site. The show received as many as 2,254 tweets on the social networking site, even before the show ended its premiere telecast^[53] and reached to more than 3800 tweets on the day.^[45] The hashtag #SatyamevJayate began trending in the morning and continued to stay at the top through to the end of the day.^[55] Next, the show's official site, satyamevjayate.in, was crashed within minutes of the end of the first episode due to huge traffic. The site posted the message, "Thank you for your overwhelming response to Satyamev Jayate. Unfortunately our servers have crashed due to the traffic, will be back soon."^[21] Also Satyamev Jayate was the top search in India on Google Trends.^[45] As of May 2012, the show's official page on Facebook has received more than 1,451,202 likes of which 233,000 likes were received on the day of its premiere.^[59] The first episode also opened many discussions on video sharing site YouTube, wherein, people left emotional messages on the

site. "A man who wanted a boy said that after watching the show he cried and he apologized to his wife and said that he just wants her to be happy," said Khan when talking to media.^[60] Hindustan Times conducted an online poll asking the viewers, "Did you like Aamir Khan's Satyamev Jayate?" to which 88% viewers agreed that they liked the show, 5% felt that Khan and the show failed to impress and 7% remained undecided, waiting to watch more episodes before forming their opinion.^[55]

Persistent Systems Ltd, an Indian IT consultancy, was the analytics (insights) partner for this show. Season 1 of Satyamev Jayate garnered 1.2 Billion impressions on the web sites.^[61] It ranked as the most talked about new show on the social media in the world.^[62] Gigaom^[63] quoted that "Satyamev Jayate, one of India's highest-rated television shows, is using data as a means to effect meaningful change". Persistent Systems used The Big Data Solution to help Satyamev Jayate keep track of how its viewership is interacting with the show. The show aggregated viewers responses from Social Media (Facebook, Twitter and YouTube), Satyamev Jayate Website (SpeakUp and Dis Qus) as well as from dedicated phone lines for the show. Variety of languages used in the responses, different formats of the responses and the need of unearthing more sentiments from the messages were challenging for the analytics team. The most responses came in Hinglish, a mix of Hindi and English. They were in either text, audio or video format. The analytics were beyond just Praise and Criticism. Persistent Systems had more than 50 tags available for every episode for message analysis.^[64] Star India Network's Chief Marketing Officer Gayatri Yadav couldn't believe what social media did was far beyond anything even beyond producers anticipation . It took the show and made it the people's show" about the response from social networking sites.

The first episode aired on may 2012 had such good connect.....

Common Topics of Discussion:

1. After the pilot episode, viewers have initiated conversations related to the theme of the episode "female infanticide". This shows that Satyamev Jayate is evoking people to discuss socially sensitive issues
2. Satyamev Jayate is being compared with The Oprah Winfrey Show. The audience is pondering over whether Satyamev Jayate is just another copy of a famous western TV show or does Aamir have something interesting.
3. Satyamev Jayate is being abbreviated to SMJ expressing the shows popularity.

SOCIAL MEDIA SNAPSHOT OF SATYAMEV JAYATE

Exhibit 1: Buzz trend over the period of observation

AUDIENCE SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

The overall opinion on “Satyamev Jayate” is positive, with just 5% talking negatively about it.

Exhibit 2: Sentiment Analysis of Audience

Gender Demographics

Majority of people talking about “Satyamev Jayate” are male. In spite of the fact that the pilot episode spoke about females and foeticide, men were conversing more about “Satyamev Jayate” than females.

Exhibit 3: Gender Demographics

Age Demographics

People in the age group of 18-35 years generate maximum of the buzz. This generation is certainly more concerned about key issues the country is facing.

Exhibit 4: Age distribution of Social Media Audience

Exhibit 5: Distribution of locations among Social Media Audience

Measuring the Social Impact

Themed on “Female Infanticide” the pilot episode of Satyamev Jayate aired on May 6th 2012 calls for a change in the society and to root out social evils existing across the social strata. The impact of the call for social change is measured in the Social Media Space. Total amount of conversations tracked: 13,632

Does the Khan-Ka-Khandan Magnet work?

In this section we try to answer the question “Does a celebrity magnet work?” If it works, to what extent it is working and if not why is it not working. Joy @JoyDas in his tweet says, “If u Check SMJ Hash tag, you will find 95% talking about Aamir Khan – 5% about Female Foeticide! And that puts our Priorities in Perspective”. His claim is not backed by a strong research data, but this guesstimate might be true to some extent.

80%. It is clear that using a celebrity as the face of the show is definitely influential in the Indian society. But to what extent? We will find out in the next section.

Exhibit 7: Social Media trend | Impact of Aamir Khan

Once the Celebrity gives an initial push, the next step depends on the quality of the content being delivered. It can be observed from **Exhibit 8** that the buzz created by a celebrity is a fad and dies down within a day. But even after excluding the entire buzz relating to "Aamir Khan" around the show, it is clear that a high quantity of buzz persists. This buzz around the show while excluding the celebrity face continues to increase.

Exhibit 9: Performance of Buzz after the launch of the show "Satyamev Jayeta"

(<http://simplify360.com/blog/social-media-analysis-on-satyamev-jayate-a-national-sensation-captured-by-social-media-buzz/>)

References for case study Satyamev Jayate:

1. **Jump up** ^ "Aamir's 'Satyamev Jayate' to be aired on private channels and DD1 simultaneously". CNN-IBN. 14 April 2012. Retrieved 14 April 2012.
2. ^ Jump up to: ^{a b} "I'm excited about my TV show: Aamir Khan". Hindustan Times. 22 October 2011. Retrieved 2 April 2012.
3. **Jump up** ^ "Satyamev Jayate Season 2 to be commence from March 2". IANS. Biharprabha News. Retrieved 26 January 2014.
4. **Jump up** ^ "Aamir Khan, the crusader?". Mid-Day. NDTV Movies. 6 May 2012. Retrieved 4 June 2012.
5. **Jump up** ^ "Aamir Khan's chat show likely on Star Plus". Indian Express. 17 September 2011. Retrieved 2 April 2012.
6. ^ Jump up to: ^{a b c d e f} Bhat, Varada (24 April 24). "STAR bets on Aamir's Midas touch in his TV debut". Rediff. Retrieved 27 April 2012.
7. ^ Jump up to: ^{a b c d e} "Aamir says he was jittery when he signed up for TV". Zee News. PTI. 13 April 2012. Retrieved 27 April 2012.
8. **Jump up** ^ "Aamir Khan: I am scared about my TV show". Rediff. 13 April 2012. Retrieved 13 April 2012.
9. ^ Jump up to: ^{a b c} "Meant for private, national channels, Aamir's show to make history". Zee News. IANS. 13 April 2012. Retrieved 27 April 2012.
10. **Jump up** ^ "Fire on Aamir Khan's upcoming TV show set". NDTV. 25 January 2012. Retrieved 18 April 2012.
11. **Jump up** ^ "Aamir Khan moves TV show to YRF". Emirates 24/7. 27 February 2012. Retrieved 18 April 2012.
12. **Jump up** ^ "When Aamir got adamant about Satyameva Jayate". Daily Bhaskar. 10 April 2012. Retrieved 4 June 2012.
13. ^ Jump up to: ^{a b} "Aamir Khan to launch music album for TV show 'Satyamev Jayate'". Zee News. Zeenews Bureau. 7 April 2012. Retrieved 30 April 2012.
14. **Jump up** ^ "'Satyamev Jayate' music album to release digitally on Hungama". RnM Team. RadioandMusic. 4 May 2012. Retrieved 8 May 2012.
15. **Jump up** ^ "Sukhwinder sings for Aamir's TV show". Zee News. IANS. 18 April 2012. Retrieved 30 April 2012.
16. **Jump up** ^ "Composer of songs: Ram Sampath". Retrieved 23 August 2012.

17. **Jump up** ^ Composer of songs: Ram Sampath
18. **Jump up** ^ Aam Ke Aam Honge Lyrics - Satyamev Jayate season 2
19. **Jump up** ^ "Palash Sen sues 'Satyamev Jayate' for plagiarism". New Delhi: IBN Live. 7 May 2012. Retrieved 7 May 2012.
20. **Jump up** ^ "'Satyamev Jayate': Nation rejoices while Palash fumes". Zee News. Zeenews Bureau. 7 May 2012. Retrieved 8 May 2012.
21. ^ Jump up to: ^a ^b "Satyamev Jayate' official site crashes". Hindustan Times. IANS. 6 May 2012. Retrieved 28 May 2012.
22. **Jump up** ^ "No 'Satyameva Jayate' for Karnataka!". Zee News. Zeenews Bureau. 4 May 2012. Retrieved 7 May 2012.
23. ^ Jump up to: ^a ^b "Aamir Khan's Satyamev Jayate to be allowed in Karnataka?". Hindustan Times. IANS. 6 May 2012. Retrieved 7 May 2012.
24. **Jump up** ^ "Aamir Khan requests KFCC for dubbing Satyamev Jayate". Oneindia.com. 3 May 2012. Retrieved 9 May 2012.
25. **Jump up** ^ "Satyameva Jayate Kannada version hits internet". Oneindia.com. 7 May 2012. Retrieved 9 May 2012.
26. **Jump up** ^ "Aamir TV show books morning slot". Hindustan Times. 11 April 2012. Retrieved 12 April 2012.
27. **Jump up** ^ "Meant for private, national channels, Aamir's show to make history.". NY Daily News. 13 April 2012. Retrieved 13 April 2012.
28. **Jump up** ^ "Aamir Khan breaks all rules.". The Times of India. 12 April 2012. Retrieved 13 April 2012.
29. **Jump up** ^ "Special screening of Satyamev Jayate in villages". Daily News and Analysis. IANS. 6 May 2012. Retrieved 8 May 2012.
30. **Jump up** ^ Awaasthi, Kavita (6 May 2012). "Aamir Khan specially screens Satyamev Jayate in villages". Hindustan Times. Retrieved 8 May 2012.
31. **Jump up** ^ CNBC-TV18 (11 May 2012). "Satyameva Jayate: Hit or miss?". Moneycontrol. Retrieved 16 May 2012.
32. **Jump up** ^ "Watch: Teaser of Aamir's TV show 'Satyamev Jayate'". Star Plus. 2 April 2012. Retrieved 2 April 2012.
33. **Jump up** ^ "Aamir Khan's debut TV show gets great money start". Rediff. 12 April 2012. Retrieved 18 April 2012.
34. **Jump up** ^ "Satyamev Jayate: Aamir Khan plans Rs 6.250 crore campaign". IBN Live. 10 April 2012. Retrieved 18 April 2012.
35. **Jump up** ^ Awaasthi, Kavita (28 April 2012). "Aamir Khan's Satyamev Jayate song to be aired in cinemas.". Hindustan Times. Retrieved 28 April 2012.
36. **Jump up** ^ "Aamir Khan promotes Satyameva Jayate in Kochi". Hindustan Times. ANI. 3 May 2012. Retrieved 28 May 2012.
37. **Jump up** ^ "Aamir's Satyamev Jayate makes history.". Hindustan Times. 13 April 2012. Retrieved 13 April 2012.
38. **Jump up** ^ "Aamir's Satyamev Jayate song finally out.". Hindustan Times. 13 April 2012. Retrieved 17 April 2012.

39. **Jump up** ^ Jha, Nilabh (26 May 2012). "Satyamev Jayate app launched for iOS". IBN Live. Retrieved 28 May 2012.
40. **Jump up** ^ "Satyamev Jayate app beats Instagram on Appstore!". Dainik Bhaskar (New Delhi). 25 May 2012. Retrieved 28 May 2012.
41. **Jump up** ^ Singh, Ritu (6 May 2012). "Satyamev Jayate: Aamir Khan's TV show is a movement". IBN Live. Retrieved 28 May 2012.
42. ^ Jump up to: ^a ^b Uniyal, Parmita (6 May 2012). "TV Review: Aamir Khan strikes the right chord with Satyamev Jayate". Hindustan Times. Retrieved 7 May 2012.
43. **Jump up** ^ Sankar, Gayatri (6 May 2012). "Review: Aamir Khan's 'Satyamev Jayate' stirs souls". Zee News. Retrieved 8 May 2012.
44. ^ Jump up to: ^a ^b ^c ^d "Aamir Khan's a desi oprah!". NY Daily News. HT Media Limited. 6 May 2012. Retrieved 7 May 2012.
45. ^ Jump up to: ^a ^b ^c Sheikh, Aminah (6 May 2012). "'Satyamev Jayate' a hit on social media". Live Mint. Retrieved 7 May 2012.
46. **Jump up** ^ Verma, Sukanya (6 May 2012). "Don't be cynical about Aamir's 'Satyamev Jayate', watch it!". Rediff.com. Retrieved 26 May 2012.
47. **Jump up** ^ Desai, Santosh (21 May 2012). "Aamir, an entrepreneur, has reconciled the market with activism". Outlook India. Retrieved 28 May 2012.
48. **Jump up** ^ Jha, Subhash (11 May 2012). "Aamir couldn't show genuine feeling!". The Times of India. TNN. Retrieved 28 May 2012.
49. **Jump up** ^ Bhatt, Sheela (8 May 2012). "Aamir Khan's Satyameva Jayate played it safe". Rediff.com. Retrieved 26 May 2012.
50. ^ Jump up to: ^a ^b ^c ^d "Aamir Khan's Satyamev Jayate takes Twitter by storm". Hindustan Times. 6 May 2012. Retrieved 8 May 2012.
51. **Jump up** ^ "TV no longer the idiot box: Madhur Bhandarkar". Zee News. IANS. 6 May 2012. Retrieved 8 May 2012.
52. **Jump up** ^ "Salman Khan praises Aamir Khan for Satyamev Jayate". 19 June 2012.
53. ^ Jump up to: ^a ^b "Aamir Khan's Satyamev Jayate top five trends on Twitter". Indo Asian News Service. NDTV. 6 May 2012. Retrieved 8 May 2012.
54. **Jump up** ^ "Aamir Khan's TV debut in Satyamev Jayate gets a thumbs up from Bollywood". Press Trust of India. NDTV. 6 May 2012. Retrieved 8 May 2012.
55. ^ Jump up to: ^a ^b ^c "HT Poll Result: Aamir's Satyamev Jayate touches hearts". Hindustan Times. 6 May 2012. Retrieved 7 May 2012.
56. **Jump up** ^ "'Satyamev Jayate' gutsy, sensible show: Viewers". IBN Live. IANS. 6 May 2012. Retrieved 28 May 2012.
57. **Jump up** ^ "Aamir Khan's Satyamev Jayate high on TRP". Hindustan Times. Agencies. 15 May 2012. Retrieved 28 May 2012.
58. **Jump up** ^ IANS (8 May 2012). "After Satyamev Jayate, 1 lakh people dial in to speak to Aamir Khan". Daily News and Analysis. Retrieved 8 May 2012.
59. **Jump up** ^ "Satyamev Jayate Likes". Facebook. Retrieved 28 May 2012.

60. **Jump up** ^ "One-episode-old Satyamev Jayate strikes emotional chord with TV viewers". India Today. Headlines Today Bureau. 6 May 2012. Retrieved 7 May 2012.
61. **Jump up** ^ SMJ Impact, Satyamev Jayate Impact Dashboard.
62. **Jump up** ^ Twitter Animation
63. **Jump up** ^ How India's favorite TV show uses data to change the world, Persistent Systems Helps Satyamev Jayate with Data Analytics
64. Persistent's journey of Satyamev Jayate
65. Indian TV Show Uses Social Media Analytics to Rally Viewers Around Social Change Persistent Systems Enables Social Media Analytics for Satyamev Jayate
66. Lahiri, Tripti (6 May 2012). "India's Oprah, Aamir Khan". Wall Street Journal. Retrieved 9 May 2012.
67. Razdan, Esha (6 May 2012). "TV review: Satyamev Jayate is not flawless, but still a potential hit". Daily Bhaskar. Retrieved 4 June 2012.
68. "Satyamev Jayate TVR". Television TRP. Retrieved 9 July 2012.
69. "Satyamev Jayate TVR". Television TRP. Retrieved 9 July 2012
70. <http://businesstoday.intoday.in/story/why-advertisers-are-happy-with-satyamev-jayate/1/187193.html>.

Reference for origin of reality shows.

1. Hill, Annette (2005). Reality TV: Audiences and Popular Factual Television. Routledge. ISBN 0-415-26152-X.
2. **Jump up** ^ Clissold, B.(2004). Candid Camera and the origins of reality TV: contextualizing a historical precedent. In Holmes, and Jermyn, D. (eds) Understanding Reality Television. London: Routledge, 33-53.
3. **Jump up** ^ McCarthy, A. (2009). Stanley Milgram, Allen Funt and me: Postwar Social Science and the First Wave of Reality TV. In Ouellette, L. and Murray, S. (eds). Reality Television Culture. New York: NYU Press.
4. **Jump up** ^ Rowan, Beth (July 21, 2000). "Reality TV Takes Hold". Infoplease.com. Retrieved May 8, 2007.
5. **Jump up** ^ Alex McNeil, Total Television (New York: Penguin Books, 1996), p. 178
6. **Jump up** ^ "Syracuse.com - Guest column: These new reality hunting TV shows are out of control". Retrieved October 17, 2013. The Post-Standard newspaper, Syracuse, New York, December 21, 2012, by Tom Adessa. "As a teenager, I always looked forward to Sunday afternoons when I'd watch Curt Gowdy and his TV show, 'The American Sportsman.' Gowdy had a distinct, soft-spoken demeanor and the destinations of his hunts were in various parts of the world."
7. **Jump up** ^ "'The American Sportsman' Penetrates the Awesome World of the Shark". Retrieved October 17, 2013. The News and Courier newspaper, February 8, 1975, Charleston, South Carolina. "Peter Benchley's journey to the world of the White Shark is an evocative portrait of one of nature's extraordinary phenomena, the shark, and of one man's revealing transition from the world of fantasy to the world of underwater reality. The American Sportsman is produced and directed by Neil Cunningham and hosted by Curt Gowdy."
8. **Jump up** ^ Baracaia, Alexa (October 4, 2006). "Warhol 'reality' film named in top 100". Evening Standard.
9. **Jump up** ^ Biressi, Anita (2005). Reality TV: Realism and Revelation. London: Wallflower Press. pp. 64–66. ISBN 1904764045.
10. **Jump up** ^ James, Caryn (January 26, 2003). "Bachelor No. 1 And the Birth Of Reality TV". The New York Times. Retrieved March 18, 2009.
11. **Jump up** ^ Oceanquest at the Internet Movie Database

12. **Jump up**[^] Peterson, Karla (November 6, 2007). "With writers on strike, expect more repeats and dose of reality". San Diego Union-Tribune.
13. **Jump up**[^] Source: Zeven werklozen samen op zoek naar een baan by Raymond van den Boogaard, NRC Handelsblad, September 28, 1996
14. **Jump up**[^] Keveney, Bill (October 9, 2007). "MTV's 'Real World' launched a revolution". USA Today.
15. **Jump up**[^] "Charlie Brooker's Screenwipe - Reality TV Editing". YouTube. February 2007.
16. **Jump up**[^] Sigismund, B. J. (October 11, 2001). Will Reality TV Survive? Newsweek. Retrieved from Lexis Nexis database.
17. [^] Jump up to:^a ^b Punathambekar, Aswin (2010). "Reality TV and Participatory Culture in India". *Popular Communication* **8**: 241-255. doi:10.1080/15405702.2010.514177.
18. **Jump up**[^] Levin, Gary (May 8, 2007). "'Simple economics': More reality TV". USA Today.
19. **Jump up**[^] Snider, Mike (March 5, 2010). Life. "Have a PlayStation? You can watch 'The Tester' ; Reality series is available only on consoles". USA Today. p. D.12. Retrieved October 10, 2010.
20. **Jump up**[^] Molloy, Tim (March 13, 2012). Reality Ratings Slip: Aging Bachelors, Idols and Dancers Lose Their Bite. The Wrap. Retrieved March 14, 2012.
21. **Jump up**[^] Margaret Lyons and Jen Cotton (January 31, 2012). "See a Venn Diagram Connecting Reality-TV Shows". New York Magazine Vulture blog.
22. **Jump up**[^] Republicans fueling record Duck Dynasty ratings, urbanites tuning out. Retrieved August 27, 2013.
23. mona sinha,2012 "Session 4: Reflections On Story In The News Media"

Reference for psychological impact of reality shows.

1. Norma pecora ,john p.murray, Ellen.a. wartella, (2006) " the impact of television on children's emotional and social development" (children and television: 50 years of research, published by Erlbaum press,june 2006 in journal media psychology, volume 8, number 1 pages 25-37.
2. (Grimes, William, G, 2012) "Attitude Adjustment: The Impact of Professional Wrestling on Adolescents" American Psychological Association, 6th edition.
3. Steven J. Kirsh (2003) "The effects of violent video games on adolescents:The overlooked influence of development",(Department of Psychology, SUNY-Geneseo, Geneseo, NY 14454, USA).
4. . (Penzhorn, Heidi, and Magriet Pitout (2007) "A critical-historical genre analysis of reality television." *Communication: South African Journal for Communication Theory & Research* 33.1 (2007): 62-76. *Communication & Mass Media*)
5. (Millon, Theodore (2004). *Personality Disorders in Modern Life*, p. 4. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, New Jersey. ISBN 0-471-23734-5.)
6. (Kassin, Saul; Fein, Steven; Markus, Hazel Rose (2008). *Social Psychology* (7 ed.). Boston, NY: Houghton Mifflin Company. ISBN 0-618-86846-1.)
7. (Aronson, Elliot; Wilson, Timothy D; Akert, Robin M (2010). *Social Psychology* (7 ed.). Prentice Hall.)
8. (Markus, Hazel (1977). "Self-Schemata and Processing Information". *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* (35): 63-78.
9. (Cialdini, R.B (2000). *Influence: Science and Practice*. Allyn and Bacon.

10. (Forsyth, D.R (2006). Group dynamics. Belmont, CA: Thomson-Wadworth.)
11. Ferris smith,green berg,smith,(2007), “ the content of reality shows and viewers perceptions of dating”. Journal of communication ,57(3) 490-510.
12. Calvert (2000), “ voyeur nation: media, privacy,and peering in modern culture”, boulder company, west view press.
13. Bente and feist (2000) “ affect talk and its kin” in D.zilliman and P.vorderer (edits) “ media entertainment: the psychology of its appeal” (pp 113-134).
14. Reiss and wiltz (2004), “why people watch reality tv”. Media psychology 6(4),363-378.
15. Mccracken,(1989), “who is a celebrity endorser? Cultural foundations of the endorsement process”. Journal of consumer research, 16 (3) 310-321.
16. A. Stefanone,Derek lackaff,devan rosen,(2010) “ the relationship between traditional mass media and social media: reality television as a model for social networking site behaviour”. Journal of broad casting and electronic media 54(3), 2010 pp 508-525 ISSN 0883-8151.
17. A. Rubin (1983) “ television uses and gratification : the interactions of viewing patterns and motivations”. Journal of broad casting 27, 37-52.
18. Nabi,beily,morgan,and stitt (2003) “ reality based television programming and the psychology of its appeal”. Media psychology,303-330.
19. Jone (2003) “ show your real face”. New media and society, 5 (3),400-421.
20. Thompson (2001) “ reality and future of television”. Television quarterly, 31 (4), 20-25.
21. Jagodozinki (2003) “ the perversity of (real)ity tv: a symptom of our times”. Journal for the psychoanalysis of culture and society, 8(2), 320-329.
22. Griffen-foley, (2004) “ from tit-bits-to-brother: a century of audience participation in the media”. Media culture and society,26 (4), 533-548.
23. A. Rubin (1994) “ media uses and effect: a uses and gratifications perspective” in j. Bryant and d. Zillmann (eds) “ media effects: advances in theory and research” pp. 417-436.
24. Fetveit (1999) “ Reality tv in the digital era: A paradox in visual culture?”. Media,culture and society,21 787-804.
25. Mendelson and papacharissi (2005) “ Reality v/s fiction: how defined realness affects cognitive and emotional responses to photograph”, paper presented at association for education in journalism and mass communication annual conference, san Antonio,IX.
26. 1. Andrejevic (2002)“ the kinder gentler gaze of big brother: reality tv in the era of digital capitalism”. New media and society,4 (2) 251-270.
2. Andrejevic (2004) “ reality tv : the work of being watched.” Oxford,u.k: rowan and littlefield publishers, inc.
27. Wong (2001) “ here’s looking at you: reality tv, big brother and Foucault”. Canadian journal of communication 26, 33-50.
28. Kilborn (1994) “ how real can you get?” European journal of communication 9(4) 421-439.
29. Gardyn (2001) “ the tribe has spoken” American demographics, 23 (9), 34-40.
30. Dauncey (1996) “reality television: more than a matter of taste?” European journal of communication, 11(1), 83-106.

31. Kaminer (2000) " I spy", the American prospect; 11 (18) pp41.
32. Ryan,Richard Edward.l.deci (2000) " Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations: classic definitions and new directions. Book contemporary educational psychology 25 (1) pp54-67.
33. reiss, steven (2002) " Who am I ? the 16 basic desires that motivates our actions and define our personalities". Berkley trade. ISSN: 978-0425183403.
34. Mannell, R.c Isho-ahola's (1987) " the psychological nature of leisure and tourism experience" annals of tourism research 14 : 314-331.
35. A. Maslow. (1954) " motivation and personality". New York harper pp 236. ISSN: 0060419873.
36. Alderfer c.p (1972) " Existence, relatedness and growth: human needs in organizational settings" newyork,free press,1972.
37. R.w. white (1963) " Ego and reality in psychoanalytic theory" Newyork, international universities press
38. Atkinson, john, joelo raynor (1978) " personality, motivation and achievement" hemisphere publications corporation. ISBN 04070993367.
39. Kassin, saul (2007) " social psychology" ISBN 0618868461.
40. Schacter, Daniel (2011) " psychology". Worth publishers
41. J.a Ouellette (1998) " habit and intention in everyday: the multiple processes by which past behaviour predicts future behaviour" psychological bulletin 457-481.
42. Lauhana ganguly (2012) "the cultural sway of the market: cultural adaptation of reality tv formats and socio cultural change in india" thesis submitted to international service of American university.